

THE MOTHER I AM

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In the morning of my life
 As I gazed upon the sunrise
 I started to awe
 From the wondrous view
 Presented before my eyes
 Of pure love and mystery
 That is unfolding right before me.

I see my life
 In the eyes of my little children
 So innocent and pure
 Meek as a sheep
 Yet gentle as the wind
 That breathes life
 And inspiration
 As I live life
 Day by day.

But what is my essence?
 The purpose of my existence
 But to love and nothing but to love
 'Tis my mission
 To continue His creation
 With these little children
 Life's fusion
 Come into completion.

I desire not
 Of matters temporal
 For all these things
 Shall come to an end
 It is my heart's desire.
 As I see them grow
 To live in beauty
 In wisdom and virtue

For these shall not pass
 But remain immortal
 In their hearts
 And in their minds.

The mother I am
 It's all that I am
 There is no greater joy
 This life can offer
 But to give life
 To these children
 I call mine
 No sweeter love
 But to bear
 The joy of
 Of bringing angels
 'Tis the essence of
 Being a woman
 Of being a mother
 The carrier of life.

The life I breathe
 Is not mine to keep
 But my breath I give
 To these frail bodies
 That in the fullness of time
 According to God's plan
 The souls I bore
 From my sacred womb
 Shall discover and know
 The joy of loving
 And the beauty of living.

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